

MINIMIZATION OF SINK MARKS FOR INJECTION MOULDED KENAF/PP COMPOSITES IN INJECTION MOULDING PROCESS BY USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHOD

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the moulding parameter of injection moulded kenaf/PP composites using Autodesk Simulation Mouldflow Insight 2014 software in order to minimize sink mark depth by optimising parameters have been analysed. The mouldability of the prototype sample which is in the shape of a car battery tray (CBT) was investigated through the numerical simulation analysis. Response surface method (RSM) adopting a Box Behnken design is used to optimise and analyse the data obtained from experimental work in order to understand the relationship between different parameters towards the sink mark depth of kenaf/PP with 20 wt% kenaf. Data obtained from optimization results will be used on the injection moulding machine in order to compare sink mark depth with numerical simulation. The combined effects of mould temperature (A), melt temperature (B), packing pressure (C), packing time (D) and cooling time (E) which affects the sink mark depth were investigated. A set of experimental runs based on various combinations of injection moulding via Minitab 17 were established. Optimum conditions for injection moulded Kenaf/PP composites were the following: mould temperature, melt temperature, packing pressure, packing time, cooling time and sink depth are 30 °C, 190 °C, 83.7 MPa, 13 s and 0.17 mm, respectively. Results are encouraging and the proposed methodology could be used effectively in minimising sink mark depths.

1 INTRODUCTION

This research is significant to analyse and predict the mould defect that is the sink mark depth a polymer composite component of the injection moulding process. The various methods have been identified to predict defects in the thermoplastic components among them are the numerical simulation [1]. The production of plastic injection moulding components has increased to the highest thermoplastic processing up to one-third of all thermoplastic processing [2]. The first generation of composites with wood-based reinforcement has been on the market for some 20 years now, and the market is expected to grow in the injection moulding industry [3].

The formation of sink mark is a phenomenon observed in thick areas where there is not enough plastic supplied or the thicker portion of the part shrinks with a greater amount than that of the thinner portion [4]. Sink marks are generated as the plastic contacting the mould walls cools and hardens before the inner plastic starts to cool down, and hence the surface is pulled inward by shrink. Therefore, sink marks which appear on the external surface of the part, are one form of such moulding defects.

Injection moulding is one of the significant net shape forming processes for thermoplastic polymers and polymer composites. Injection moulding is suitable for the production of large quantities of products and complex shapes. Injection moulding has become a challenging process for manufacturers and researchers to produce high-quality products and low cost. In a competitive environment, the trial-and-error approach to determine the process parameters for injection moulding is no longer practical. As the plastics products reveal extremely complicated material properties, the moulding process

becomes very challenging to attain desired part properties and thus causes difficulty in maintaining quality products during production [5].

In plastic injection moulding, process parameters play a significant role in product quality. The industry is looking for a cost-effective new manufacturing method to reduce the overall manufacturing cost. The manufacturing method known as plastic injection moulding offers a more cost-effective manufacturing process for the commercial production of complex plastic products. However, detailed studies are needed to obtain an optimum process parameter to produce the products without any defects such as warpage, sink marks and others at minimum manufacturing cost.

Presently, various techniques have been implemented to reduce the sign of sinkings, such as by the Taguchi method [6, 7] and the RSM approach [8]. This analysis can apply to the process setting and the various parameters which can help avoid or reduce the moulding defects on the moulded plastic component. RSM is a technique for finding the link between several processing parameters and its performance with several defined standards and confirms the acceptance of this processing. RSM also performs statistically designed of experiments, estimates coefficients in a mathematical model and predicts response and checking the adequacy of model [9, 10]. Hence, RSM is a collection of mathematical and statistical procedures and is decent for the modelling and analysis of problems in which the desired response is affected by numerous variables [11, 12].

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The design of the car battery tray is remodeled in 3D CAD systems using the CATIA V5 software based on the original design as shown in Fig. 1. This model is then translated into STL or IGES files before being included in the Autodesk Simulation Mouldflow Insight 2014 (ASMI) software. The material flow simulations on the model will be run with the ASMI software according to the predefined parameters. The car battery tray (CBT) was designed using CATIA software and then imported into the Mouldflow analysis software as shown in Fig. 2. Next, kenaf 30%wt/PP composite was selected as the material for this research. During the process, RSM Box Behnken with five processing parameter and three levels were applied. Table 1 shows the list of processing and levels of the process.

Figure 1: CBT model in Catia V5

Figure 2: CBT model in Mouldflow

Factor	Parameter	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
A	Mould temperature	35	52.5	70
B	Melt temperature	170	185	200
C	Packing pressure	24.6	54.15	83.7
D	Packing time	12.1	16.1	20.1
E	Cooling time	15	17.5	20

Table 1: Parameters and levels used for simulation

The RSM Box-Behnken design was used and the software generates 46 runs involved in this study and it was adopted as an experimental design through MPI simulation software. The results obtained from the MPI simulation will then be analyzed using the Minitab 17 software using the Response Surface Method (RSM) experimental design method (DOE) to obtain optimum parameters for the net shape product through the injection moulding process. The levels of each process parameter in this study were selected according to actual production experience. Materials used in this study are Polypropylene supplied by Lotte Chemical Titan (M) Sdn. Bhd. and kenaf fibre was obtained from the National Kenaf and Tobacco Board, which is the diameter of kenaf between 17.7 – 21.9 μm , length is 2-6 mm, the density of kenaf is 1.4 g/cm^3 , tensile strength is 930 MPa, and flexural strength is 98 GPa [13].

Materials used in this simulation are kenaf fibres with a load of 30 wt% while the polymer matrix is 70 wt% PP of Lotte Chemical Titan (M) Sdn. Bhd. The required material grade can be selected in ASMI 2014 material database. There is much information related to the selected material can be found in select material dialogue in the software. The parameters used in this study are mould temperature, melting temperature, packing pressure, packing time and cooling time. While the injection moulding machine used as the simulation of this study is the Demag IntElect 100/420 model as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Injection moulding machine Demag Intelect 100/420 model

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Second-order productivity model development

The depth of sink mark for the composite is between 0.22 mm to 0.60 mm. The lowest sink depth

value is 0.22 mm at the mould temperature (35 °C), melt temperature (190 °C), packing pressure (83.7 MPa), packing time (16.1 s) and cooling time (17.5 s). The highest sink depth value was obtained at 0.60 mm under mould temperature test conditions (70 °C), melt temperature (190 °C), packing pressure (24.6 MPa), packing time (16.1 s) and cooling time (17.5 s).

The statistical study of the sink mark depth for this composite was investigated using MINITAB 17 software through RSM and the effect of the independent variables into the response is shown in Table 2.

Runs	Code level					Real variable					Response
	A	B	C	D	E	A (°C)	B (°C)	C (MPa)	D (s)	E (s)	Sink mark depth (mm)
1	-1	-1	0	0	0	35	170	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.27
2	1	-1	0	0	0	70	180	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.35
3	-1	1	0	0	0	35	200	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.33
4	1	1	0	0	0	70	200	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.53
5	0	0	-1	-1	0	52.5	190	24.6	12.1	17.5	0.49
6	0	0	1	-1	0	52.5	190	83.7	12.1	17.5	0.23
7	0	0	-1	1	0	52.5	190	24.6	20.1	17.5	0.48
8	0	0	1	1	0	52.5	190	83.7	20.1	17.5	0.27
9	0	-1	0	0	-1	52.5	180	54.15	16.1	15	0.3
10	0	1	0	0	-1	52.5	200	54.15	16.1	15	0.41
11	0	-1	0	0	1	52.5	180	54.15	16.1	20	0.3
12	0	1	0	0	1	52.5	200	54.15	16.1	20	0.41
13	-1	0	-1	0	0	35	190	24.6	16.1	17.5	0.44
14	1	0	-1	0	0	70	190	24.6	16.1	17.5	0.6
15	-1	0	1	0	0	35	190	83.7	16.1	17.5	0.22
16	1	0	1	0	0	70	190	83.7	16.1	17.5	0.31
17	0	0	0	-1	-1	52.5	190	54.15	12.1	15	0.31
18	0	0	0	1	-1	52.5	190	54.15	20.1	15	0.34
19	0	0	0	-1	1	52.5	190	54.15	12.1	20	0.31
20	0	0	0	1	1	52.5	190	54.15	20.1	20	0.39
21	0	-1	-1	0	0	52.5	180	24.6	16.1	17.5	0.38
22	0	1	-1	0	0	52.5	200	24.6	16.1	17.5	0.6
23	0	-1	1	0	0	52.5	180	83.7	16.1	17.5	0.25
24	0	1	1	0	0	52.5	200	83.7	16.1	17.5	0.28
25	-1	0	0	-1	0	35	190	54.15	12.1	17.5	0.27
26	1	0	0	-1	0	70	190	54.15	12.1	17.5	0.38
27	-1	0	0	1	0	35	190	54.15	20.1	17.5	0.31
28	1	0	0	1	0	70	190	54.15	20.1	17.5	0.47
29	0	0	-1	0	-1	52.5	190	24.6	16.1	15	0.34
30	0	0	1	0	-1	52.5	190	83.7	16.1	15	0.26
31	0	0	-1	0	1	52.5	190	24.6	16.1	20	0.48
32	0	0	1	0	1	52.5	190	83.7	16.1	20	0.26
33	-1	0	0	0	-1	35	190	54.15	16.1	15	0.3

34	1	0	0	0	-1	70	190	54.15	16.1	15	0.44
35	-1	0	0	0	1	35	190	54.15	16.1	20	0.3
36	1	0	0	0	1	70	190	54.15	16.1	20	0.44
37	0	-1	0	-1	0	52.5	180	54.15	12.1	17.5	0.28
38	0	1	0	-1	0	52.5	200	54.15	12.1	17.5	0.34
39	0	-1	0	1	0	52.5	180	54.15	20.1	17.5	0.3
40	0	1	0	1	0	52.5	200	54.15	20.1	17.5	0.46
41	0	0	0	0	0	52.5	190	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.33
42	0	0	0	0	0	52.5	190	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.33
43	0	0	0	0	0	52.5	190	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.33
44	0	0	0	0	0	52.5	190	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.33
45	0	0	0	0	0	52.5	190	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.33
46	0	0	0	0	0	52.5	190	54.15	16.1	17.5	0.33

Table 2: Parameter response value used in Box-Behnken design

3.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for sink depth

Table 3 shows the variance analysis for sink mark depth of kenaf/PP composite. Factor A, B, C and D are representing the mould temperature, melt temperature, packing pressure, packing time and cooling time, respectively. From the ANOVA analysis, the model is significant with a P-value of 0 [14]. It can be concluded that the significant models have the primary influence on the mould temperature, melt temperature, packing pressure and packing time with P-value is 0. Meanwhile, for squares, the main significant is the mould temperature and packing pressure with the P-values are 0.001 and 0.006, respectively.

On the other hand, for two-stage interactions, the model is significant which has the primary influence of AB (mould and melt temperature), BC (melt temperature and packing pressure) and CE (packing pressure and cooling time) with P-values are 0.022, 0.001 and 0.009, respectively. The regression accuracy shows that the adjusted R^2 and R^2 values are 96% and 92.8%, respectively. Hence, this contributes to 3.2% between the difference in R^2 and R^2 adjusted values. Therefore, it can be considered that the data analysis is accurate because the difference between the adjusted R^2 and R^2 values does not exceed 20%. Therefore, this model is accepted for further prediction and analysis.

Factor	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P	
Model	20	0.363	0.018	29.880	0.000	significant
A – Mould temperature	1	0.073	0.073	119.870	0.000	
B – Melt temperature	1	0.054	0.054	88.880	0.000	
C – Packing pressure	1	0.187	0.187	307.570	0.000	
D – Packing time	1	0.011	0.011	17.280	0.000	
E – Cooling time	1	0.002	0.002	3.710	0.066	
A ²	1	0.008	0.008	13.830	0.001	
B ²	1	0.002	0.002	4.090	0.054	
C ²	1	0.006	0.006	9.120	0.006	
D ²	1	0.000	0.000	0.180	0.675	
E ²	1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.980	
AB	1	0.004	0.004	5.920	0.022	
AC	1	0.001	0.001	2.010	0.168	
AD	1	0.001	0.001	1.030	0.320	

AE	1	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000
BC	1	0.009	0.009	14.840	0.001
BD	1	0.003	0.003	4.110	0.053
BE	1	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000
CD	1	0.001	0.001	1.030	0.320
CE	1	0.005	0.005	8.060	0.009
DE	1	0.001	0.001	1.030	0.320
Error	25	0.015	0.001		
Lack of fit	20	0.015	0.001		
Pure error	5	0.000	0.000		
Total	45	0.379			
Standard deviation		0.025			
R ²		0.960			
R ² adjusted		0.928			
R ² prediction		0.839			

Table 3: Analysis variance of sink mark depth

3.3 Interaction Parameter on sink depth

Fig. 4 and 5 show the contour plot relationship between mould temperature (A), melt temperature (B), packing pressure (C), packing time (D) and cooling time (E) towards the sink mark depth. Fig.6 and 7 show the 3D plot of the relationship between mould temperature (A), melt temperature (B), packing pressure (C), packing time (D) and cooling time (E). From Fig. 5 shows the lowest sink depth at low mould and melt temperature values. Whereas, Fig. 6 shows the lowest sink depth at the high packing pressure and cooling time. From Fig. 7 shows that the combination of low mould and melt temperature contributes towards the low sink depth values. Meanwhile, the surface plot of sink depth vs packing pressure and cooling time in Fig. 8 shows the high packing pressure and cooling time values contribute to the low sink depth.

Figure 4: Contour plot of sink depth vs melt temperature (B) and mould temperature (A)

Figure 5: Contour plot of sink depth vs packing pressure (c) and cooling time (e)

Figure 6: Surface plot of sink depth vs melt temperature (b) and mould temperature (a)

Figure 7: Surface plot of sink depth vs cooling time (e) and packing pressure (c)

3.4 Mathematic model for sink depth

The relationship of the varied parameters towards the response can be demonstrated by the mathematical model that offered in RSM. Based on the sink depth values obtained from the analysis, mathematical equations have been developed to estimate the depth of sinking through all the factors involved using numerical model codes. The predicted sink depth can be calculated by replacing the variables with a general equation, linear and mould temperature interactions (A), melting temperature (B), packing pressure (C), packing time (D) and cooling time (E) in equation 1 (regression equation in uncoded unit).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sink depth} = & 3.50 - 0.02380 A - 0.0298 B + 0.0211 C - 0.1132 D + 0.0091 E + 0.000078 A^2 + \\ & 0.000075 B^2 + 0.000029 C^2 + 0.000221 D^2 + 0.00003 E^2 + 0.000100 AB - 0.000030 AC + 0.000156 \\ & AD - 0.0000 AE - 0.000107 BC + 0.000417 BD + 0.000106 CD - 0.000474 CE \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The parameter variables that can be identified and optimized to reduce the depth values of the moulded section through the simulation can be seen through the MINITAB software on the response optimization section. This software will identify important process parameters that contribute to sink depth defects to minimize potential defects. The results for sink depth on the moulded battery tray after optimization are presented in Table 4.

Factor	Parameter setting optimization
Mould temperature, A (°C)	30
Melt temperature, B (°C)	190
Packing pressure, C (MPa)	84
Packing time, D (s)	13
Cooling time, E (s)	20
Sink depth prediction (mm)	0.20
Sink depth actual (mm)	0
Product thickness (mm)	15.25
Error (%)	1.3

Table 4: The results of sink depth for injection moulded battery tray after optimization

From Table 4 it is found that the error percentage value is 1.3% than 10% indicates the accuracy of the model is very good. Whereas error less than 30% indicates the accuracy of the model is acceptable. Subsequently, the error is less than 50%, the accuracy of the model is very low and if more than 50% model accuracy is rejected [15]. Therefore, based on the results of Table 4, the accuracy of the model is very good or significant.

3.5 Experimental verification run

This experiment designed for injection moulding process is verified by a numerical simulation analysis with the contribution from Table 4. The sink marks will be seen in a thick area of the product as shown in Fig. 8. The optimization parameters will be incorporated into the machine control system and then be processed to perform the injection process.

Figure 8: A cutting plane of the CBT model

The second verification run, which is conducted with a mould temperature of 30 °C, melt temperature of 190 °C, packing pressure of 84 MPa, packing time of 13 s and a cooling time of 13 s. The sink mark value predicted is 0.2 mm. Fig. 9 shows injection moulded CBT results that have no effect on sink mark.

Figure 9: The final CBT product after optimization

4 CONCLUSIONS

As for the conclusion, the optimum parameter for injection moulding parameters towards the quality characteristics of prototype made from kenaf/PP composite had been achieved. This study has used the RSM method to estimate the optimum solution of the injection moulding process which leads to minimize the sink depth. The proposed model can also be used in the design stages for refine the product geometry. It can eliminate disruptions during production and improper dependence on general guidelines and thumb rules. Continuous research in this direction can lead to more comprehensive and appropriate guide lines for designers and moulders. Table 5 as a guide lines to designers and moulders for troubleshooting. The results show the ability of this approach to minimise sink mark for various combination of processing variables with in the design area.

Moulding defect	Parameter setting				
	Mould temperature	Melt temperature	Packing pressure	Packing time	Cooling time
Sink depth	Low	Low	High	Long	Long

Table 5: Sample of injection moulding defect and solution

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